

The Factors Driving the Success of the Film-Brand Alliances

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Abstract

The growing popularity of brand alliances between film characters and brands has attracted public attention, encouraging companies to collaborate with the film industry in the form of brand alliances as a marketing initiative. However, persuading prospective collaborators to adopt these marketing initiatives involving film in order to grow their brand remains a significant challenge for licensors. Meanwhile, businesses continuously seek approaches to profit from their products or services. The main objective of this research is to analyze the relationships between familiarity, entertainment, emotional value, symbolic value, and brand alliance attitude in film–brand collaborations that can influence consumers’ willingness to pay more. The findings indicate that consumers’ willingness to pay more (WTPM) is significantly influenced by brand alliance attitudes shaped by familiarity with film and brands, entertainment, and customer-perceived values such as emotional and symbolic value. This research offers suggestions for future studies, along with theoretical and managerial implications for brand owners and film licensors.

Keywords: Film-Brand, Co-Branding, Brand Alliance, Willingness to Pay More

INTRODUCTION

In a commercial business, a brand is the most essential part that guarantees the success of a business (Blackett & Russell, 2000). In this digital era, brands have shown significant development in their marketing. This situation has led to increasingly fierce competition between brands. With the arrival of newcomer brands, simply offering a good quality product to consumers is no longer enough. Brands are demanded to grow at a fast pace with a more innovative approach in creating marketing strategies that are able to capture consumer attention, increase customer experience, and push the growth of the business. Therefore, co-branding is a business opportunity for a brand to grow its brand awareness and differentiate itself from its competitors (Beem, 2010). Co-branding or also known as brand alliance, is a form of alliance between two or more brands that involves a formal contractual agreement that brings profits for both or all parties involved (Keller et al., 2013), where the owner of the brand or intellectual asset acts as a licensor that gives authorization to the other party, namely the licensee, to produce and sell products that make use of the licensor's brand or assets (Atuahene-Gima et al., 1992). The brands involved in the co-branding will introduce their combined brands into one or more products; therefore, it creates a greater impact in the market compared to solely using one brand (Ahn et al., 2020; Newmeyer et al., 2018).

Films have always been used as entertainment media for consumers, but nowadays, films have become a potentially strong marketing platform for brands (Popova, 2026). With the widespread use of co-branding as a strategy in recent years, many commercial companies have implemented co-branding to intensify brand awareness, enhance brand value, and distinguish

their brands from competitors (Besharat et al., 2014; Newmeyer et al., 2014). Barbie is an example that represents the success of a co-branding strategy between a film and a commercial brand (Nur, 2023). Film characters with a huge fanbase often create cultural phenomena on digital platforms (Film Threat Staff, 2025). The 2023 live-action Barbie film starring Margot Robbie and Ryan Gosling has created a sense of nostalgia among fans who grew up watching Barbie. The release of the Barbie film became a huge success for commercial brands, as Barbie doll sales increased by up to 16 percent to USD 605 million compared to the same period in the previous year (Forsdick, 2024). Moreover, MINISO released exclusive Barbie collections that offered various kinds of items, including makeup, bags, stationery, and lifestyle essentials featuring Barbie's trademarks, namely the pink color and Barbie logo. This co-branding product by MINISO x Barbie received significant attention from fans through its collaboration products and a real-life Barbie Dreamhouse-designed store, which led to a significant increase in product sales of around 30%, breaking MINISO's record on the first day of the product launch (Christina, 2023).

Although co-branding has been widely implemented by large brands, which mostly involve collaborations between commercial brands such as Nike x Supreme (Wilson, 2020) and Adidas x Gucci (Adidas, 2022), research specifically related to co-branding between films and brands is still limited. Existing studies have first explored that the suitability of brands plays an essential role in the success of co-branding (Bluemelhuber et al., 2007; Johan et al., 2012). Second, compatibility between brands in an alliance is able to affect consumer behavior toward co-branding (Helmig et al., 2007; Riley et al., 2015). Suitable brands for co-branding result in a

positive influence on overall brand implementation (Ma et al., 2018). By implementing co-branding, businesses are able to increase their profits on the condition that they collaborate with brands that are relatively similar in terms of the quality they offer (Cao et al., 2017). However, these studies tend to emphasize brand fit rather than predictors such as consumer attitudes toward brand alliances (Desai et al., 2002; Gammoh et al., 2006). Furthermore, previous research has also discussed brand alliances between film characters, specifically superhero characters, and brands, rather than exploring co-branding more generally, such as film-brand collaborations (Monika and Antonio, 2022). These studies on co-branding and brand alliances have helped improve understanding of customer behavior in responding to co-branding strategies and identifying several variables that can affect how customers evaluate brands, particularly film-brand collaboration products

Referring to the Theory of Reasoned Action (TRA) (Fishbein, 1967), this theory explains that consumer behavior can be predicted based on their evaluations. Additionally, Consumer-Based Brand Equity (CBBE) (Keller, 1993) discusses brand alliances between brands as a means to increase the value of a product or service offered to consumers. Moreover, due to the limited research regarding film-brand alliances, this study addresses this gap by offering a new schema with a theoretical framework to examine the correlation between several variables, such as familiarity, entertainment, emotional value, and symbolic value derived from a film, which can influence consumer attitudes toward brand alliances and how co-branding could contribute to consumers' willingness to pay more. This study therefore addresses the following research questions:

- RQ1. How do film characters help brands and contribute to the development of co-branding?
- RQ2. To what extent do familiarity, entertainment, emotional value, and symbolic value of film characters positively affect the success of co-branding?
- RQ3. What is the most essential aspect of using a film character in collaboration with a brand that leads to consumers' willingness-to-pay-more behavior?

By addressing these research questions, this study makes three contributions to the film industry and particularly to the literature on commercial brands. First, this study provides information regarding how film characters help brands create emotional connections, entertainment value, and symbolic value that strengthen consumer perceptions toward the parties involved in the brand alliance, leading to positive brand attitudes and encouraging consumers' willingness to spend more. Second, this study also provides four indicators that are able to increase consumer engagement, strengthen positive perceptions, and create a memorable experience toward the brand alliance. Thirdly, this research explores the ability of a film character to create emotional and symbolic value for consumers leads to a strong brand attitude and increases consumers' willingness to pay extra due to the personal connection and experience they have with the film character.

LITERATURE REVIEW & HYPOTHESES

Co-branding

The fundamental framework in this research refers to the Theory of Reasoned Action (TRA) (Fishbein, 1967), which states that consumer evaluations can forecast consumer behavior in the future. In accordance with this theory, one's intention results from an evaluation or attitude toward something or a product that influences their behavior (Longwell, 1991). In a marketing context, consumers are more likely to use, prefer, and support a brand toward which they hold a positive impression (Keller, 1993). The core subject of this study corresponds to consumer intention, specifically willingness to pay more.

Besides that, this research also covers the concept of brand alliances, which is the approach of combining two or more brands in order to increase value from the buyer's perspective. Keller's Consumer-Based Brand Equity (CBBE) theory is applied to fully understand how consumers evaluate brand associations (Keller, 1993). Based on this theory, consumers' perceptions, experiences, and sense of connection define brand value. Consumers are more likely to value and recall a brand if they have a positive impression, experience, and feel closely associated with it.

Direct effects of Familiarity and Entertainment

Emotional responses that arise in response to consumer stimuli are not confined to simple feelings of liking or disliking; rather, they also include several other emotions, such as happiness, hatred, and fear, which are far more complex (Holbrook et al., 1982). Furthermore, Sweeney and Soutar (Sweeney et al., 2001) described emotional value as an advantage that a person receives from a product or service based on its ability to enhance certain feelings, such as emotional

interest or happiness. In the context of this research, emotional value refers to consumers' feelings when they use a film-brand collaboration product, which creates a memorable experience for users.

Symbolic value, in contrast, is associated with the way buyers perceive an item as an instrument to fulfill their desires and social expectations in society. This indicates that an object is valued and seen not merely for its functionality, but also as a platform to show one's position in society, self-worth, and sense of belonging within a certain community (Hunt et al., 1997). In practical terms, impressions toward one another are often based on how people use a certain product or how they present themselves (Hunt et al., 1997).

Moreover, brand familiarity represents the level of how familiar the consumer is with a brand, acquired through informational knowledge (Baker et al., 1986). The frequency of consumer interaction with a brand results in a closer connection with brands they engage with or obtain information from more often (Alba et al., 1987; Kent et al., 1994). Familiarity with a brand is more likely to evolve and become part of an individual's identity once they are aware of and more familiar with a brand (Beggan et al., 1994; Pierce et al., 2003). The term "familiarity" in this research describes how consumers develop a connection with a film character and a brand based on their past interactions and the knowledge they have gained throughout their lives.

Hypotheses 1a: Familiarity has a positive effect on emotional value.

Hypotheses 1b: Familiarity has a positive effect on symbolic value.

An experience that stimulates responses such as excitement, fascination, and pleasure is known as entertainment (Bosshart et al., 1998; McKee et al., 2014). Entertainment is perceived in terms of consumerism as a form of excitement created by a product or service that potentially delivers customers a hedonic experience (Holbrook and Hirschman, 1982). In marketing, entertainment helps build a positive brand image and enhances the quality of the consumer experience (Holbrook, 2000). Consumer experiences such as shopping tend to make them feel happy and satisfied (Sit et al., 2003). Meanwhile, this research emphasizes film characters as part of an ongoing trend in the entertainment industry (Hammonds, 2021). In addition, past research has shown strong evidence that entertainment can influence consumer emotions (Elmashhara et al., 2019) and their perceptions of value (Chen et al., 2018; Kim et al., 2009).

Hypothesis 2a: Entertainment has a positive effect on emotional value

Hypothesis 2b: Entertainment has a positive effect on symbolic value

Mediating role of Emotional and Symbolic Value

The overall impression that the public has of a brand is identified as brand attitude (Kotler et al., 2005). Meanwhile, a brand alliance is an agreement of partnership between multiple brands that decide to share their assets to produce new products, services, or promotional activities in the market (Park et al., 1996). As stated by Simonin and Ruth (Simonin et al., 1995), a brand alliance is a mutual agreement to collaborate between two or more brands to combine their resources for a certain period of time to release a new product or service in the

market. In terms of contractual partnership, namely “brand licensing,” a brand provides another brand with authorization to utilize the licensor’s name, logo, and other brand-related assets for its products or services in exchange for licensing fees (Ferrell et al., 2014). The main objective of brand collaboration in this research is brand licensing, especially in cases where commercial brands use film character licensing in the products and services they offer to consumers.

Hypothesis 3: Emotional value has a positive effect on brand alliance attitude.

Hypothesis 4: Symbolic value has a positive effect on brand alliance attitude.

Mediating Role of Brand Alliance Attitude

Consumers are likely to be more willing to spend extra money when they hold positive perceptions toward a brand (Aaker, 1991). The term “willingness to pay” (WTP) indicates the amount of money consumers are willing to spend to own a specific product or service (Cameron et al., 1987; Krishna, 1991). WTPM focuses on the willingness of buyers to pay a higher price than what would be considered the reasonable cost (Rao et al., 1992). WTPM is not merely concentrated on consumer purchase intention, but also serves as a measure of positive attitudes (Rodrigue et al., 2004) toward a brand alliance. WTPM is strategically important for commercial brands, as it can contribute to higher profitability and larger market share (Haumann et al., 2014; Tang et al., 2017).

Hypothesis 5: Brand alliance attitude has a positive effect on willingness to pay more

Indirect Effects of Familiarity and Entertainment

The role of familiarity on WTPM, as stated by Kuncoro (2023), is defined by the level of association a consumer has with a brand, which can create consumer experiences. As a result of consumers engaging with the brand and gaining easier access to information about it, familiarity with the brand can develop in the consumer's mind, leading them to spend money. Widely recognized brands with strong familiarity are more likely to be on consumers' purchase lists. Especially brands that offer good quality will make consumers willing to pay extra for the product or service.

In terms of consumerism, entertainment is a form of excitement created from products or services that can generate an attitude where consumers are willing to pay money to gain such experiences (Holbrook and Hirschman, 1982). The experience that shopping offers is able to make consumers feel happy (Sit et al., 2003). That is why consumers are willing to spend more money to experience it.

Hypothesis 6: Familiarity has a positive effect on willingness to pay more.

Hypothesis 7: Entertainment has a positive effect on willingness to pay more.

Sequential Mediation Effect

Due to constant exposure and the accumulation of information, consumers develop familiarity with a brand and film character, which leads to positive emotional reactions (Baker et al., 1986). Having positive emotional experiences can build the emotional connection consumers perceive from the product (Beggan et al., 1994; Pierce et al., 2003). This helps strengthen brand

alliance attitudes, particularly for collaboration products between film characters and brands, which is therefore expected to make consumers willing to spend more on an item they have a positive impression of (Aaker, 1991).

Familiarity also helps in creating perceived meanings of a brand or product, leading to increased symbolic value. Consumers are more likely to identify a product with social recognition, self-worth, and self-expression when they are more associated with film characters (Hunt et al., 1997). Their evaluation of the brand alliance is enhanced by the perceived symbolic value, which ultimately results in a positive brand alliance attitude and increases consumers' willingness to spend more money (Aaker, 1991).

Hypothesis 8a (H8a). Familiarity has a positive influence on willingness to pay more through emotional value and brand alliance attitude.

Hypothesis 8b (H8b). Familiarity has a positive influence on willingness to pay more through symbolic value and brand alliance attitude.

Consumers' positive emotional experiences, such as excitement and thrill, are enhanced by perceived emotional value (Sweeney et al., 2001) that they receive from products and film characters. Offering products such as film-themed products can strengthen consumers' perceived emotional value. This leads to a positive brand attitude and consumers' willingness to pay extra money (Aaker, 1991).

Film characters are one of the aspects of the entertainment industry that allow consumers to utilize what they have bought as a way to express their identity, lifestyle, and sense of belonging (Hunt et al., 1997). This elevates the symbolic value of the product, which encourages a positive brand alliance attitude and increases consumers' willingness to pay more (Aaker, 1991).

Hypothesis 9a (H9a). Entertainment has a positive influence on willingness to pay more through emotional value and brand alliance attitude.

Hypothesis 9b (H9b). Entertainment has a positive influence on willingness to pay more through symbolic value and brand alliance attitude.

The research framework was constructed from existing research by Monika and Ferdi Antonio (2022). The hypotheses and relationships between variables in this framework can be seen as follows (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Research framework

METHODS

Research Setting

This research gathers data collected by an accumulation of measurable indicators. Market research was done by collecting respondents that are aware of brand alliance between film characters and commercial brands. This study used a quantitative based approach that gathers respondents using a survey method through distributing online questionnaires specifically to consumers that are familiar and have experienced with the collaboration product of film and brand. The data obtained were then analyzed to test the relationships between the variables formulated in the research hypothesis.

Measurement

The indicators to gather respondents were adapted from existing literature to ensure the data collected were measured with reliable indicators. Each of the variables were measured utilizing 6 variables, such as: Ha and Perks (2005) provided familiarity; entertainment adopted by Mathwick et al. (2001), Van-Tien Dao et al. (2014), and Bruner et al. (1998); emotional value was provided by Sweeney and Soutar (2001); symbolic value is collected from Zhang and Zhao (2019) and Liu et al. (2020); and brand alliance attitude constructed from Simonin and Ruth (1995). Lastly, the willingness to pay more was developed by Saha et al. (1998) and Bruner et al. (1998). All items are measured from the indicator using a seven-point Likert scale, in which 1 indicates “strongly disagree” and 7 represents “strongly agree.”

Sample & Data Collection Procedure

We adopted a screening approach at the starting point of our online survey in order to filter out selected respondents that are familiar, aware, and experienced with the co-branding marketing approach between film industry and commercial brands products or services whether by online or offline. There’s four questions as a filter for respondents to answer (Appendix 1): (1) From several examples of film-brand collaborations above, have you ever seen a film-brand collaboration? (2) From the following list, which film-brand collaboration products have you seen? (3) How often do you see brand collaborations with films? (4) Where do you usually see these collaborations? After completing each corresponding filter question, respondents were able to proceed with the rest of the survey questions.

RESULTS

An overall 146 survey respondents were collected that meet the requirements of this research. The gathered respondents' data were presented in [Appendix 2](#). With the majority of 89 women respondents (61%) around z generations who are university students. About 139 respondents are aware of film-brand collaboration before, representing 97.2%, followed by 4 others who have never seen film-brand collaboration before (2.8%).

This research adopted a Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modeling (PLS-SEM) using a SmartPLS to analyse the measurement and structural models, with 32 items found to be valid. This method was chosen out of the complexities of the research model that involves simultaneous analysis (Hair et al., 2019). PLS-SEM methods are very effective in analyzing complex models which is ideal for explorative study such as present study. As well as supporting this study goal which is a prediction tool to investigate relationships predictively for our study (Becker et al., 2012; Hair et al., 2016). We analyze data in this study with SmartPLS™ version 4.1.1.8. Technically, this study evaluation is processed in two steps that includes outer model and inner model. The outer model works to construct reliability and validity of the data collected, meanwhile the inner model works to test the relations between the constructs in the research model.

Analyzing the outer model is the beginning step of the PLS-SEM model analysis procedure (Sarstedt et al., 2017). There are few indicators that are eliminated due to failure in meeting the appropriate value of (> 0.7) according to the outer loading shown in [Appendix 3](#) and Average Variance Extracted (AVE) (> 0.5) to be concluded as acceptable. The outer loadings in this study are in the range of 0.724 to 0.943 and the AVE scores are ranging from 0.598 to 0.843.

Cronbach's alpha (CA) and construct reliability (CR) values are used in this research in order to aid in evaluating the reliability of the items. The minimum level of CR and CA must not be under 0.70 (Hair et al., 2019). According to [Appendix 4](#), it shows that all indicators have a CA and CR value above 0.70, which shows that all indicators met the requirements that means they are reliable and valid for this study.

The [Table 1](#) below exhibits the outputs of the R-Square test. The R-Square values of the model were ranging from 0.283 to 0.517 which shows that all the variations are weak to moderate effects in this research model.

Table 1. Result of R-Square

Variable	R-Square	R-Square adjusted
Brand Alliance Attitude	0.517	0.51
Emotional Value	0.469	0.461
Symbolic Value	0.283	0.272
WTPM	0.516	0.505

The Fornell Larcker criterion is known as a tool to identify discriminant issues and is used to conduct a discriminant validity test. All square roots of the AVE values are greater than the highest correlations with other constructs, which is consistent with the results presented in [Appendix 5](#) below. This indicates that all indicators in this model are well discriminated in evaluating their respective constructs.

Table 2. Path Coefficient.

Path	β	Standard Deviation	T-value	P-value	Decision
Familiarity -> Emotional Value	0.149	0.087	2.012	0.044	Accepted
Familiarity -> Symbolic Value	0.193	0.092	2.35	0.019	Accepted
Entertainment -> Emotional Value	0.599	0.092	6.223	0.000	Accepted
Entertainment -> Symbolic Value	0.419	0.106	3.59	0.000	Accepted
Emotional Value -> Brand Alliance Attitude	0.453	0.103	3.817	0.000	Accepted
Symbolic Value -> Brand Alliance Attitude	0.344	0.114	3.373	0.001	Accepted
Brand Alliance Attitude -> WTPM	0.512	0.092	5.559	0.000	Accepted

Familiarity -> WTPM	0.178	0.107	1.631	0.103	Rejected
Entertainment -> WTPM	0.131	0.131	1.065	0.287	Rejected

Table 2 represents the output of the path coefficient test. The outcome revealed that emotional value is positively affected by familiarity ($\beta = 0.174$, t -value = 2.012, p -value < 0.05) and symbolic value is positively impacted by familiarity ($\beta = 0.217$, t -value = 2.35, p -value < 0.05). The results pointed out the significance of Hypotheses 1a and 1b. Moreover, entertainment also had a significant impact on emotional value ($\beta = 0.573$, t -value = 6.223, p -value < 0.05) and symbolic value ($\beta = 0.38$, t -value = 3.59, p -value < 0.05). We can conclude that both Hypothesis 2a and 2b are accepted.

Furthermore, emotional value ($\beta = 0.393$, t -value = 3.817, p -value < 0.05) and symbolic value ($\beta = 0.384$, t -value = 3.373, p -value < 0.05) also shown a positive impact to consumer's brand alliance attitudes. Which shows that Hypothesis 3 and 4 are accepted. Besides that, WTPM is significantly affected by brand alliance attitude ($\beta = 0.509$, t -value = 5.559, p -value < 0.05) indicating acceptance as a result in Hypothesis 5.

However, when it comes to correlation of familiarity to WTPM ($\beta = 0.174$, t -value = 1.631, p -value > 0.05) and entertainment to WTPM ($\beta = 0.139$, t -value = 1.065, p -value > 0.05), this relationship was found to result in no statistically significant impact. This would imply the rejection of Hypotheses 6 and 7.

Table 3. Path Coefficient of Sequential Mediation Effect.

Path	β	Standard Deviation	T-value	P-value	Decision
Familiarity -> Emotional Value -> Brand Alliance Attitude -> WTPM	0.034	0.022	1.553	0.120	Rejected
Familiarity -> Symbolic Value -> Brand Alliance Attitude -> WTPM	0.034	0.021	1.629	0.103	Rejected
Entertainment -> Emotional Value -> Brand Alliance Attitude -> WTPM	0.139	0.054	2.589	0.010**	Accepted
Entertainment -> Symbolic Value -> Brand Alliance Attitude -> WTPM	0.074	0.041	1.820	0.069*	Accepted

*A p-value measures the error rate and p should be <0.05. *p<0.1, **p<0.05, ***p<0.01, ****p<0.001.*

Path coefficient test of the sequential mediation effect output is shown in [Table 3](#). The result concluded that familiarity is not significant on willingness to pay more through emotional value and brand alliance attitude ($\beta = 0.034$, t-value = 0.022, p-value is rejected) and familiarity is also not significant on willingness to pay more through symbolic value and brand alliance attitude ($\beta = 0.034$, t-value = 0.021, p-value is rejected). These findings indicated that Hypothesis 8a and 8b is not significant. Furthermore, entertainment had a significant impact on willingness to pay more through emotional value and brand alliance attitude ($\beta = 0.139$, t-value = 0.054, p-value < 0.05) and entertainment had a significant impact on willingness to pay more through symbolic value and brand alliance attitude ($\beta = 0.074$, t-value = 0.041, p-value < 0.1). We can conclude that both Hypothesis 9a and 9b are accepted.

DISCUSSION, IMPLICATIONS AND FUTURE RESEARCH

Discussion

This study aims to examine the factors affecting familiarity and entertainment, which in turn shape consumers' brand alliance attitudes and WTPM through the mediating role of perceived emotional and symbolic value. The data were gathered through a quantitative research method using SEM-PLS to analyze the data.

The results indicate that consumers' perceived emotional and symbolic value are significantly influenced by familiarity and entertainment. These findings imply that customers are more likely to develop a stronger emotional attachment and symbolic value toward collaboration products or services when they are more familiar with products associated with a certain brand or film that they like.

Furthermore, the research showed that brand alliance attitudes are significantly influenced by emotional and symbolic value. This study indicates that consumers do not merely perceive film-brand alliances based on the functionality, practicality, and advantages of the products offered. Rather, consumers also perceive emotional satisfaction, personal meaning, and the product as a medium to express themselves.

Moreover, it was found that customers' WTPM is significantly affected by brand alliance attitudes. This suggests that buyers are more willing to spend more on collaboration products when they have a positive attitude toward film-brand alliances.

The sequential mediation effects consisting of familiarity, entertainment, emotional value, symbolic value, brand alliance attitude, and WTPM were further examined in this research. The findings show that Hypotheses 8a and 8b do not represent significant sequential mediation paths. These results indicate that even when emotional and symbolic value evaluations play a role, familiarity may be insufficient to increase consumers' WTPM. However, the sequential mediation effects of Hypotheses 9a and 9b were found to be significant. This indicates that entertainment has a greater impact on forming emotional and symbolic value, which can build positive brand alliance attitudes and encourage buyers' willingness to pay more. As a result, entertainment appears to be a stronger driver than familiarity in developing consumers' positive perceptions toward film–brand alliances.

Theoretical implications

The main objective of this research is to analyze variables such as familiarity and entertainment that affect consumers' emotional and symbolic value, which subsequently shape brand alliance attitude and willingness to pay more. The outcomes of this study validate the significant relationships of the proposed hypotheses by illustrating the relationships in the conceptual model.

The results of this study point out that consumers' willingness to pay more is greatly affected by brand alliance attitudes shaped by familiarity and entertainment, which influence consumers' emotional and symbolic value. The findings above are aligned with existing studies that reported that WTPM can be influenced by a positive brand attitude (Yodpram et al., 2020; Popovic et al., 2020; Rodrigue et al., 2004). Furthermore, consumers will develop a positive attitude toward the brand alliance once they recognize the film character trademark on the product; therefore, they are more likely to be willing to spend more on the particular product they purchase.

Findings from this research showed a relationship corresponding to brand alliance attitude. Both emotional and symbolic value help shape consumers' brand alliance attitudes. The results provided are consistent with previous research (Hammonds, 2021; Elmashhara et al., 2019), which stated that film characters are in great demand because of their entertainment value, showing that buyers of film–brand collaboration products are strongly influenced by their perceptions of film characters as engaging and capable of creating happiness and satisfaction as they use the purchased products.

This study makes three contributions to the literature on film–brand alliances. First, the present study reveals how film characters help brands create emotional connections, entertainment appeal, and symbolic value, which strengthen customers’ positive evaluations of both companies involved in the collaboration. These results could lead to a positive brand attitude and encourage consumers to increase their spending. Second, this research proposes four indicators that could potentially increase engagement, maintain positive sentiments, and create a memorable brand alliance experience. Third, the research explores how a film character’s capability to trigger emotional and symbolic value helps develop a positive brand attitude and increases consumers’ WTPM due to the personal connection and experience associated with the film.

Managerial implications

According to the evaluation, several managerial implications are proposed. Brands or licensors are expected to acquire new prospective partners as a way to further grow their businesses. When proposing a brand marketing initiative involving film, brands can apply the findings of this study to convince potential partners regarding the potential benefits that film can offer. In order to optimize the successful outcomes of brand alliances, management could strategically select films that are known to have strong customer familiarity and entertainment appeal among the public.

Brands need to work more on maximizing film capability to generate entertainment value. They are expected to allocate their resources and efforts toward showcasing the film qualities to capture audience attention and demonstrate how film can be entertaining and enjoyable. Moreover, managers must comprehend that consumer evaluations toward film–brand alliances are not solely focused on the functionality of the products offered, but also on self-expression, emotional connection, and experience.

Therefore, brands need to develop collaboration-based products and marketing initiatives that can generate meaningful and pleasurable customer experiences. The use of storytelling, limited-edition collaboration items, interactive campaigns, engaging programs, and well-designed appealing products can amplify the alliance between brands, particularly in terms of the emotional and symbolic value perceived by consumers. Brands could increase their revenue and sales by creating alliances with film while implementing competitive pricing strategies. As a result, brands will gain a stronger brand image and have the potential to attract prospective customers. Nevertheless, both parties, namely the licensor and licensee, should initially evaluate whether the specific film character, types of products, and target customers are an ideal fit for the brand alliance agreement. Hedonic products could potentially be more suitable for such alliances.

Lastly, consumers' willingness to spend more is significantly driven by a positive brand alliance attitude. From a long-term perspective, brands can strengthen consumers' willingness to pay more by building a competitive advantage and generating profits through consistently creating engaging, emotionally meaningful, and symbolically significant alliances. However, in order to establish an effective brand alliance strategy, brands must develop their own strong brand identity instead of simply depending on film character trademarks, such as logos placed on the products they sell.

Limitations and future research directions

Overall, this study provides an insight on how consumer behavior toward brand alliance attitudes and willingness to pay more for film-brand products and services can be predicted. Understanding these factors can help businesses better understand consumers' brand alliance attitudes and willingness to pay more.

However, there are limitations in this study that must be taken into consideration. First, the research concentrates on examining brand alliances between commercial brands and film-associated intellectual assets, which could limit the generalizability of the research to other forms of collaboration or industries. Therefore, future research could explore various kinds of entertainment-related brand alliances, for example partnerships with music artists, video game players, professional athletes, or internet celebrities, to evaluate how they affect consumer behavior. Second, to further understand the indicators that drive brand alliance performance, future research could also examine variables such as nostalgia, consumer engagement, or brand loyalty. Third, respondents' income ranges are not included in this research. It is therefore suggested that future studies examine income as a modifier of consumers' purchasing power. Lastly, data could be collected more than once to reduce the possibility of biased information.

Appendixes

Appendix 1. Respondent Screening Question

CO-BRANDING

Co-branding adalah strategi pemasaran di mana dua atau lebih brand bekerja sama dalam satu produk, layanan, atau kampanye untuk menciptakan nilai tambahan bagi konsumen.

Kolaborasi ini biasanya dilakukan untuk meningkatkan daya tarik produk, memperluas pasar, dan memanfaatkan kekuatan masing-masing brand.
Dibawah ini adalah beberapa contoh co-branding antara film populer dan brand yang bisa digunakan sebagai referensi responden terhadap maksud "co-branding" di penelitian ini.

Contoh 1 - MINISO x Disney Stitch

Contoh 2 - UNIQLO x SPY x FAMILY

Contoh 3 - Mobile Legends x Naruto

2. Dari daftar berikut, produk hasil kolaborasi film-brand mana yang pernah Anda * lihat?
Bisa pilih lebih dari 1

<p><input type="checkbox"/> Crocs X Squid Game</p>	
<p><input type="checkbox"/> Uniqlo X SPY x FAMILY</p>	
<p><input type="checkbox"/> Heinz X Marvel Studios (Deadpool & Wolverine)</p>	
<p><input type="checkbox"/> Miniso X Disney Stitch</p>	<p><input type="checkbox"/> Yang lain:</p> <hr style="width: 100%;"/>

3. Seberapa sering Anda melihat kolaborasi brand dengan sebuah film? *

1 2 3 4 5 6 7

Sangat Jarang ○ ○ ○ ○ ○ ○ ○ Sangat Sering

4. Di mana Anda biasanya melihat kolaborasi tersebut? *

Bisa pilih lebih dari 1

Instagram

Tiktok

Youtube

Iklan (TV / Billboard)

Marketplace (Shopee, Tiktoshop, Tokopedia, dll)

Toko Offline

Orang Sekitar / Word of Mouth

Yang lain: _____

Appendix 2. Respondent’s demographic profiles.

Demographic Variables		Sample (n)	Percentage (%)
Gender	Male	57	39
	Female	89	61
Age	< 17 years	3	2.1
	17-21 years	62	42.5
	22-29 years	75	51.4
	≥30 years	4	2.7
	≥40 years	2	1.4
Domicile	Jabodetabek	92	63
	Non-Jabodetabek	54	37
Occupation	University Student	87	59.6
	Business Owners	13	8.9
	Employees	37	25.3
	Others	9	6.2

Have you ever seen a film-brand collaboration?	Yes	139	97.2
	No	4	2.8

Appendix 3. Convergent validity, composite reliability and validity

Variable	Indicator	Outer Loading	CA	CR	AVE
Familiarity	FAM1: I can easily recognize the characters from the film.	0.813	0.832	0.835	0.598
	FAM2: I know about the characters from the film.	0.803			
	FAM3: The marketing techniques of film-brand collaborations are very familiar to me.	0.736			
	FAM4: I understand and comprehend the marketing techniques of film-brand collaborations.	0.724			
	FAM4: I am familiar with the products offered by film-brand collaborations.	0.787			
Entertainment	ENT1: I feel excited about seeing film-brand collaborations.	0.843	0.957	0.961	0.72
	ENT2: I feel happy about seeing film-brand collaborations.	0.843			
	ENT3: I feel excited about seeing film-brand collaborations.	0.854			
	ENT4: I find film-brand collaborations very innovative.	0.818			
	ENT5: I find film-brand collaborations very different or unique.	0.89			
	ENT6: I find film-brand collaborations a cutting-edge marketing technique.	0.836			
	ENT7: I find film-brand collaborations	0.734			

	very interesting.			
	ENT8: I find film-brand collaborations very entertaining.	0.886		
	ENT9: I find film-brand collaborations very enjoyable.	0.874		
	ENT10: I find film-brand collaborations very engaging.	0.897		
Emotional Value	EV1: I like brand products with film character logos or images.	0.782		
	EV2: I enjoy using brand products with film character logos or images.	0.898		
	EV3: Using brand products with film character logos or images makes me feel better.	0.887	0.874	0.878 0.727
	EV4: Using film-brand collaboration products gives me satisfaction.	0.839		
Symbolic Value	SV1: I enjoy being the center of attention when wearing film-brand collaboration products.	0.886		
	SV2: Film-brand collaboration products symbolize my social status and exclusivity.	0.898		
	SV3: Wearing film-brand collaboration products makes me different.	0.925	0.953	0.956 0.843
	SV4: I feel more successful when wearing film-brand collaboration products.	0.943		
	SV5: I feel more confident when purchasing film-brand collaboration products.	0.938		
Brand Alliance Attitude	BAT1: Products resulting from film-brand collaborations are more engaging.	0.892		
	BAT2: Products resulting from film-brand collaborations are more unique.	0.792	0.883	0.891 0.741
	BAT3: Products resulting from film-brand	0.888		

	collaborations have a better image.				
	BAT4: Products resulting from film-brand collaborations create an extraordinary impression.	0.867			
	WTPM1: I'm willing to pay more for branded products with official film licenses	0.925			
Willingness to Pay More	WTPM2: I don't mind paying more for branded products with film licenses due to quality assurance.	0.876	0.901	0.904	0.772
	WTPM3: I don't mind paying more for branded products with film licenses to support the film.	0.893			
	WTPM4: Price isn't a significant factor in my decision to stick with film-brand collaborations.	0.818			

Appendix 4. Discriminant Validity - Fornell Larcker

Variables	Brand Alliance Attitude	Emotional Value	Entertainment	Familiarity	Symbolic Value	WTPM
Brand Alliance Attitude	0.861					
Emotional Value	0.666	0.853				
Entertainment	0.707	0.669	0.849			
Familiarity	0.447	0.492	0.555	0.774		
Symbolic Value	0.664	0.71	0.5	0.428	0.918	
WTPM	0.686	0.653	0.596	0.479	0.671	0.879

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Vanessa Agtasia : Conceptualisation, methodology, questionnaires, design, online data collection, data analysis, manuscript preparation, and manuscript refinement fall under this category.

Natalia : In charge of formal analysis, validation, and supervision.

Open data statement :

The data are available at

Similarity check :

Similarity check was done using Turnitin plagiarism and AI detection software. The similarity index of the submission was 4% which indicates a high level of originality. As for AI detection, results show “*% detected as ai” which means the AI writing score is below 20% reporting threshold and considered non- significant. This confirms that this study represents original scholarly work developed through independent research, analysis, and writing, with any AI tools only used for limited language editing assistance.

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